

Supplementary figures to the manuscript ‘The fundamental role of character coding in Bayesian morphological phylogenetics’

Basanta Khakurel, Courtney Grigsby, Tyler D Tran, Juned Zariwala, Sebastian Höhna, and April M. Wright

This document contains the supplementary figures to the manuscript ‘The fundamental role of character coding in Bayesian morphological phylogenetics’.

Figure S1: Line plot containing marginal likelihoods for each dataset under both unpartitioned (purple and yellow) and partitioned (blue and red) models. The dataset we used was the datasets simulated with four states under the unpartitioned model. Even though these datasets were simulated under the unpartitioned model, marginal likelihood favors the partitioned model for all the simulation replicates.

Figure S2: Distributions of tree lengths when a large number of character states are unrepresented. In this set of simulations, we simulated characters with a state space of 10 and replaced either 5 states or 8 states with a ‘?’, indicating missing data. During these conditions, where a large number of states are missing from the original matrix, the branch lengths are underestimated as the number of missing character states increase.

Figure S3: Tree lengths for the trees estimated using the binarized data. In these simulations, we simulated characters under the unpartitioned model with 4, 10 and 20 states. We then rendered the characters binary by changing half of the character states to 0 and the other half to 1. Changing the character matrices to binary led the branch lengths to be underestimated as the original state space increased. When 4-state matrices are changed to binary, the effect of underestimating the branch lengths is lesser than when 20-state matrices are changed to binary.

Figure S4: Histograms showing the tree length distributions for different simulations under the unpartitioned model with small dataset. Red bars represent the tree lengths for simulations analysed under the unpartitioned model and the cyan bars represent the tree lengths when the analysis is partitioned by state. Similar to Fig. 4, complete character sampling contains all the characters whereas in missing maximum state, the largest state is replaced with missing data. The tree length for the tree that the datasets were simulated under is indicated by the black dashed line and the prior mean is indicated by the red dashed line.

Figure S5: Tree Lengths for the partitioned simulation without rejection. On the top panel of this figure is shown simulations in which 25% of characters come from a state space larger than binary, and 75% come from a binary matrix. Red bars represent the tree lengths for simulations analysed under the unpartitioned model; cyan bars represent the tree lengths for the simulations analysed under the partitioning by state model; and violet bars represent the tree lengths for the simulations analysed under the true partitioned model. The black dashed line indicates the tree length of the true tree and the red dashed line is the prior mean for the tree length.

Figure S6: Distribution of scaled symmetric difference for unpartitioned simulations. (Small dataset)

Figure S7: Distribution of scaled symmetric difference for unpartitioned simulations. (Large dataset)

Figure S8: Distribution of scaled symmetric difference for partitioned simulations. (Without rejection sampling)

Figure S9: Distribution of scaled symmetric difference for partitioned simulations. (With rejection sampling)